

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES OF GAMBLING ADDICTION IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The article examines the current problem of gambling addiction in modern Kazakhstan society. Ludomania is a problematic condition associated with gambling. Gambling addiction is common, and overcoming this behavior can be difficult. The rise of problem gambling affects the entire country, not just individuals who engage in it.

The aim of this study is to analyze the causes among young people in terms of identifying the objects and forms of gambling addiction.

Keywords: Gaming industry, gambling addiction, consequences of gambling addiction, socio-economic consequences, The main factors influencing the growth of gambling addiction in Kazakhstan

Introduction

Nowadays, it can be said that gambling addiction is on par with addictions such as drug addiction and alcoholism. Addiction to computer games is becoming a scourge of the 21st century.

For many millennia, humanity has played various games, society has developed, and games have developed from primitive (for example, dice) to high-tech (computer). Among the Kazakh people, asyk games are widespread in society, and were a mass hobby, similar to the modern hobby of some people for gambling.

The desire to play was initially perceived as a human quality. This is due to the fact that the game contributed to the knowledge and socialization of the world, mastery of production activities during the game, served as a means of physical development and leisure. For a long time, gaming addiction was considered a problem of laziness and weak will. Only in the second half of the 20th century did it begin to be considered a serious pathology, the same as alcoholism and drug addiction.

Methodology.

La méthode principale permettant de tirer de nouvelles conclusions sur le matériel de l'étude est l'analyse comparative, ainsi que la méthode descriptive et la méthode d'analogie

Main part.

Gambling includes various types of roulette, slot machines, poker, and betting in offline and online casinos. Online casinos have recently become especially popular and widespread. The word "gambling" comes from the Arabic word "alzar" - "dice" [1].

The first documented sources of gambling were found among the ruins of ancient Babylon (3000 BC). Dice was the most common game in the Middle Ages. Card games appeared in Europe during the Crusades in the 13th century. Legends say that men used their own wives, sisters and daughters as bets, as well as their own body parts, houses, cattle, etc. Until 1849, there was a

casino in Baden-Baden. The famous writer F. M. Dostoevsky often lost there, and he himself very interestingly described the state of a person during a game in the novel "The Gambler" [2]. A. S. Pushkin considered card games his strongest passion, saying that he "would rather die than not play" [3].

Ludomania is a problematic condition related to gambling. It involves an addiction to some type of compulsive behavior. When people have trouble controlling the time and money they spend on gambling, it can have negative consequences for the individual, their loved ones, and the nation as a whole.

The gaming industry emerged in the United States in the early 1970s. By the mid-1980s, video games had already become a global phenomenon. Ten years later, they had become a full-fledged part of world culture [4]. In Kazakhstan, the widespread use of gambling (casinos, slot machines, betting) can be attributed to the end of the last century, which was due to the emergence of a market economy and the development of entrepreneurial activity.

Gambling addiction can destroy families due to financial problems, lies and deception on the part of the gambler. Additional gambling problems in Kazakhstan may include the following:

Illegal gambling operations: Despite government efforts to regulate gambling, there is still an underground gambling market that operates outside of laws and regulations. This can result in a loss of tax revenue for the government.

Negative impact on youth: Gambling can have a negative impact on young people by taking them away from the education and entertainment that promote healthy development. It can also contribute to misconceptions about money and success.

Corruption and the influence of crime: Gambling can be a source of corruption, especially if it is not controlled by the state. Illegal operations can attract the attention of organized crime and become a source of illegal income.

Impact on the economy: gambling addiction can have a negative impact on a country's economy. Resources spent on gambling could be directed to more productive areas such as education, health care or infrastructure.

Cultural and social aspects: Gambling can change the socio-cultural aspects of society, including shifting values and priorities. This can lead to the loss of traditional values and social disorientation [5].

Gambling addiction can affect people of any age, but the issue is especially acute among teenagers and young people. Gambling addiction not only takes away a huge amount of the most valuable resource - time, but also stops the spiritual development of the individual, causes various mental disorders that lead to significant

health problems. It is possible to indirectly track the change in the situation with gambling addiction in Kazakhstan based on sociological research. For example, the topic of addiction to gambling is annually addressed in the work of the Youth Research Center commissioned by the Ministry of Information and Social Development. According to the results of surveys of young Kazakhstanis for 2021-2023, the share of respondents playing gambling games during this period increased from 0.1% to 3%. There is also a noticeable increase in the share of respondents who spend a lot of time playing computer games - from 11.8% to 39.5%. It is online games for teenagers and young people that become the start of destructive thinking and the onset of gambling addiction (Figure 1) [6].

Figure 1. Results of surveys of young Kazakhstanis for 2021-2023 [6].

According to the figures, the share of teenagers aged 14–18 who spend a lot of time playing computer games was 50.1% last year. In the group of adults up to 23 years old, this figure is already lower (41.8%), in the category aged 24–28 – even lower (30.5%). But in the “oldest” youth group – from 29 to 34 years old – the

share of computer gamers is already significantly higher: 40.6%. The following trend can be observed with gambling: the share of gamers increases with age. The maximum figure of 4.7% is observed in the category from 29 to 34 years old (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Results of surveys of the “older” youth group of Kazakhstanis for 2021-2023 [6].

There are several factors that currently influence the growth of gambling addiction and the number of complaints from relatives of gamblers. According to the Association for the Protection of Rights in the Gambling Business of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the online gambling business in the country is partially in the shadows. In addition to Internet companies that operate in Kazakhstan illegally, without any licenses, there are also foreign bookmakers and online casinos. Part of the money lost by Kazakhstanis "goes" to those who do not pay taxes, or abroad. The association notes that it is possible to control this process by prohibiting

payment organizations from transferring money in favor of foreign gambling companies. Another problem that aggravates gambling addiction in Kazakhstan is the lack of "stop-bans" for losing players. Unfortunately, bookmakers and casino employees are still accepting bets from people who have already lost large sums in a day. Also, at present, there are no limits on gambling for Kazakhstanis who have debts and loans.

Conclusion

The main factors influencing the growth of gambling addiction in Kazakhstan:

- the negative impact of the shadow market in the gambling business;
- weak legislative framework concerning the rights of citizens;
- openness of the medical database of addicts registered due to gambling addiction;
- no ban on games for indebted citizens;
- the influence of online advertising of online bookmaking companies, including foreign ones;
- no requirements for online identification;
- no loss limit from casinos and bookmakers [7].

Behind the allure of jackpots and the glitter of casinos lies a harsh reality - a reality where lives are shattered, families are torn apart, and hope flickers dimly in the face of addiction. Yet amid the shadows, there is a beacon of hope - a testament to the resilience of the human spirit and the transformative power of compassion and understanding.

The gaming industry provides tax revenue, employment and entertainment for society. But it also has a regressive tax structure and creates problems such as pathological gambling [8]. The outflow of international payment systems from the Russian market has led to a massive migration of Internet platforms to the Kazakhstani market. As a result, over the past 2 years, the gambling market has overtaken the real estate market and occupies a leading position on which Kazakhstanis spend the most money. It is for this reason that playfulness and gambling addiction occupy a high place among Kazakhstani youth.

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